
ORIGINAL RESEARCH ARTICLE

Shifts in Meaning Making: Impact of Context, Task and Individual Differences

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Abstract

Contemporary multimodal theory stresses how different semiotic resources can be used in meaning making. The combination of these resources (verbal and non-verbal) is described as intersemiosis. However, while context is seen as important, in practice little attention is paid to context in the presentation of research. As a result the process of resemiosis is often left implicit. This paper discusses the findings of a research design specifically focused on both intersemiosis and resemiosis in meaning making.

Keywords: Multimodality, Intersemiosis, Resemiosis, Meaning Making, Problem Based Learning

Introduction

The early focus for research using semiotics was on meaning making by speech (Halliday, 1978) and then, as developed into multimodality to take account of non-verbal communication. Both Halliday and those who developed his theories acknowledged the importance of context in influencing both the processes of information transmission and of understanding. In the usual theoretical structure of multimodality (Halliday, 1978; Kress, 2010; O'Halloran, 2008, 2011b), context is represented by the concept of Resemiosis.

Resemiosis addresses the reason why certain semiotic resources are used in particular contexts or for a given task (Iedema, 2003) and also how those resources are interpreted by the user and any observer. This basic approach is reflected in other theoretical domains such as social constructionist psychology (Augoustinos, Walker, & Donaghue, 2014; Barker, Quennerstedt, & Annerstedt, 2013; Lock & Strong, 2010) and is a core concept in the various developments of Vygotsky's cultural-historical Activity Theory (Blunden, 2011; Vygotsky, 1987) and the subsequent development of Activity Theory by Leontev (Leontev, 1978) and then Engeström (Engeström, 1999). There are similarities across these varied theoretical frameworks, in particular, that context influences understanding and actions (and vice-versa) but a significant challenge is to show how this actually happens (Cromby & Nightingale, 1999; Harris, 2013; Kaptelinin, 2005).

In a multimodal approach, context should provide the framework both to understand how semiotic resources are being used, their varying meaning and which resources are accessed. Thus our understanding of what we observe, and our appreciation of which semiotic resources to use, is heavily influenced by context. There is a linkage here to Leontev's (1978) argument that social norms constrain how a particular work task is described and indeed how it is to be carried out. In Leontev's theory this is a two way process in that new forms of work organisation in turn influence the social norms that are used to describe such tasks. In effect, context both provides clues to how to understand a situation, but also our formulation of the context provides information on how we should behave in such circumstances.

One problem in many multimodal studies is that context, and thus resemiosis, is often not explicitly coded. This has two consequences. First, there is a tendency to present the situation of a

given study such as 'a classroom' or 'a TV programme' and leave each reader to construct their own understanding from this broad information. Second, there is often little practical attention paid to how that context circumscribes and informs meaning making.

One solution to this problem is to study the semiotic resources and modes of interactions of different individuals in the same situation. In effect, is it possible to identify variations in their interaction that may reflect differences in their self-identified role in a particular situation? If so, this allows us to see if their activity reflects their different understandings.

This study took place in the context of a first year engineering class that used Problem Based Learning (PBL) to allow the students to understand some basic concepts of stress and mechanics. To do this, they were given a limited range of tools (short weak wooden sticks and glue) and asked to design a bridge of a certain length to hold a pre-defined weight. The active group studied consisted of the class tutor, who took on the role of a facilitator and five students who were meant to share the bridge building task (Choo, 2012; Cindy E. Hmelo-Silver, 2004; Cindy E. Hmelo-Silver, Duncan, & Chinn, 2007; Mills & Treagust, 2003; Savin-Baden et al., 2011). Other students were present as part of the overall class but were not observed as part of this research.

Literature Review

The study of semiotics and meaning making was given a new focus with Halliday's (1978) research in how social norms and context influenced meaning making using language. His original concept of *Systemic Functional Linguistics* (SFL) (Halliday, 1978) argues that language (written or spoken) is the dominant mode of meaning making. However, over time, Halliday's focus on language has been expanded to include a range of meaning making modes including non-verbal gestures, images and, increasingly, multimedia (Norris, 2004; O'Halloran, 2008, 2011a). The addition of extra modes of meaning making led to a need to identify how they interacted. This interaction is described as intersemiosis (Bezemer & Kress, 2008; Kress, 2010; Kress & van Leeuwen, 2006). Different modes can complement each other (Lemke, 1998), contradict each other, or, feasibly, be used to present different types of information.

So giving spoken directions, combined with a pointing gesture can be seen as being complementary. On the other hand speech, accompanied with a facial gesture that indicates disinterest, can be seen as contradictory (Terry, 2007). Finally, less commonly, it is possible that a non-verbal gesture is being used for one meaning making process and speech for another (in effect holding two 'conversations' at the same time). In most situations, one mode, usually speech (Fei, 2004), is dominant and other semiotic modes are being used to reinforce the message presented using words (Márquez, Izquierdo, & Espinet, 2006). However, the dominant mode does vary according to the task being undertaken (Lirola, 2010; Liu, 2009; Taylor, 2006; Yu, 2011).

Important though intersemiosis is, in effect it has diverted some attention from Halliday's original focus on the importance of context. Within multimodal studies, resemiosis is the manner in which the overall context gives sense to the meaning making. Thus it forms the process by which meaning shifts due to the wider context, and, in turn, changes in both context and social space affect the process by which meaning is built up (Iedema, 2003). Thus if we are told an example of meaning making comes from a science classroom there is an implicit assumption that certain rules apply. Presumably there is a teacher, who possesses some degree of authority (even if just of knowing more than the students), the underlying goal of the interaction is that the students will learn more at the end of the class than they knew at the start. Other aspects may be more variable, how much authority, what are the norms for student-teacher interaction, is there use of modern technology? All these factors may have a bearing on how both participants and observers interpret the semiotic resources in use (Jewitt, 2008; Kress, 2010; Siegel, 2006).

However, while multimodality has developed a variety of coding structures to capture and describe different semiotic resources and notation systems to show their interaction, as such resemiosis is left uncoded (O'Halloran, 2011b). This has two implications, first, the interaction between changing interpretations of the situation and semiotic usage is rarely made explicit. Second, the process of understanding the wider framework is often left to the observer to construct. An example of how coding of both individual semiotic modes and their interaction can lack explicit coverage of resemiosis is shown below:

Figure 1: Multimodal analysis including images (O'Halloran, 2011b, p. 17)

Stage	*Petrol Prices									
Phase	Leaked Cabinet Documents									
Sub-Phase	Leaked Documents as Political Issue									
	SHOT 1	SHOT 2	SHOT 3						SHOT 4	SHOT 5
Salient Visual Frame										
SEMIO TIC RESOURCE:										
Speech:										
Speaker 1 - Tony Jones (interviewer):	<i>Abright Tony Abbott</i>	<i>you've been in the trenches. That's fair enough isn't it?</i>			<i>* yes, a little - a little bit like the coalition.</i>	<i>Leaking going on all round</i>				
Speaker 2 - Tony Abbott:		<i>Ah, yes it is</i>	<i>but the interesting thing is that the new government is already</i>	<i>leaking. Tony, I mean normally it takes many years</i>	<i>*before a - before a government</i>	<i>... well I - I've had old governments</i>	<i>leak. New, smart, clever.</i>	<i>intelligent governments aren't supposed to</i>	<i>leak, and the fact that this government is leaking so badly</i>	<i>so early is a pretty worrying sign.</i>
Kinetic Features:										
Gaze:	<i>off-screen; engaged; directed at interviewer</i>	<i>off-screen; engaged; directed at Tony Abbott</i>	<i>off-screen; disengaged; directed at self</i>	<i>off-screen; engaged; directed at studio audience/interviewer/Tanya Piberssek</i>	<i>off-screen; engaged; directed at studio audience/interviewer/Tanya Piberssek</i>	<i>off-screen; engaged; directed at camera/viewer</i>	<i>off-screen; engaged; directed at studio audience/interviewer/Tanya Piberssek</i>	<i>off-screen; engaged; directed at studio audience/interviewer/Tanya Piberssek</i>	<i>off-screen; engaged; directed at Tony Abbott</i>	<i>off-screen; engaged; directed at studio audience/interviewer/Tanya Piberssek</i>
Body Posture:	<i>angled.</i>	<i>angled; leans forward toward Tony Abbott</i>	<i>angled; leans back</i>	<i>angled.</i>	<i>angled.</i>	<i>straight.</i>	<i>angled.</i>	<i>angled.</i>	<i>angled.</i>	<i>angled.</i>
Gesture:			<i>raises hand; palm facing outward</i>	<i>raises hand; palm facing outward</i>	<i>hand raised; palm facing outward</i>	<i>both hands raised; palms facing outward/each other</i>	<i>both hands raised; palms facing outward/each other; gap narrowing</i>	<i>both hands raised; palms facing outward/each other; gap narrowing</i>		<i>both hands raised; palms facing outward/each other at reduced distance; downward movement</i>
Cinematography:										
Camera Angle (horizontal perspective)	<i>oblique/detached</i>	<i>oblique/detached</i>	<i>oblique/detached</i>	<i>oblique/detached</i>	<i>oblique/detached</i>	<i>frontal/involved</i>	<i>oblique/detached</i>	<i>oblique/detached</i>	<i>oblique/detached</i>	<i>oblique/detached</i>
Size of Frame	<i>medium close-up</i>	<i>medium close-up</i>	<i>medium close-up</i>	<i>medium close-up</i>	<i>medium close-up</i>	<i>medium close-up</i>	<i>medium close-up</i>	<i>medium close-up</i>	<i>medium close-up</i>	<i>medium close-up</i>

This shows a political interview in Australia with, the then leader of the opposition, Tony Abbott. O'Halloran's (2011b) approach allows the observer to link a visual image of the speaker at each stage, to the words used and non-verbal aspects such as direction of gaze, body posture and gestures in use. In addition, the manner in which the interviewed was reported is reflected in the discussion of camera angle and frame. However, an important part of understanding what is being shown comes from the context of what to expect in a 'political interview'. The presumed norms for this process may be shared in many countries (such as Australia, the US or the UK) but are not universal (a political interview in say China would be very different). So a key part of the understanding can only come from observers sharing the knowledge that this interview was taking place in a very particular context (Johansson, 2006).

In effect, resemiosis, links to similar concepts in other theoretical frameworks such as Activity Theory and the wider field of social constructivism in arguing that our understanding of context is an important part of both how we understand what we see (or hear) and how we ourselves would participate in such a setting. However, the linkage between different understandings of the situation, and different usage of semiotic modes is often not directly studied (Iedema, 2003; Márquez, et al., 2006).

Research Design

This study looked at the different meaning making approaches adopted in a Problem Based Learning (PBL) class taken by first year engineering students. PBL varies from other approaches to either project work or student led learning in higher education in a number of critical ways. In particular, students are set a complex problem, and, at the start, will lack the information they need to resolve the task. To assist them, a subject specialist will take on the role of a facilitator helping the students by guiding them in constructing their understanding of the problem, but ideally not providing direct solutions. To reflect this process, the concept of scaffolding has become important as the means by which students are provided with clues and information designed to help them in the problem solving task (Choo, 2012).

In this case, a class of 25 students were expected to work in small groups to design a model bridge using specified resources (short wooden sticks and glue) to meet a given stress test without buckling. Of the overall class, five agreed to be video-taped when carrying out their task as did the academic leading the module (who acted as the facilitator).

In total five sessions were recorded and this produced a total of almost four hours of video tape. The focus of each session varied, with the earlier ones dominated by facilitator led discussions of the underlying theoretical concepts and the rules and expectations around the task (such as submission date, style of testing, other academic requirements and resources available). From the third session onwards, the focus shifted to building the model bridge and session four involved only two of the student group experimenting with different designs. The final session revolved around a discussion between the students and the facilitator about the validity of this design and what steps needed to be taken in order for them to meet the academic requirements of the task.

Each verbal and non-verbal gesture was coded, initially into six categories (Cindy E. Hmelo-Silver, Chernobilsky, & Jordan, 2008) of:

- 1) Content of the talk – to capture the focus on a given semiotic mode (task, tool, concept or unrelated);
- 2) Collaboration – to capture the degree of interaction, agreement, disagreement, acknowledgement of others and questioning approach used;
- 3) Responses – where appropriate, how a question was answered;
- 4) Knowledge – whether this reflected conceptual (ie engineering) knowledge or was drawn from past experiences;
- 5) Metacognition – captured either instances of monitoring of the group or individuals (mostly by the facilitator) or task planning; and,
- 6) Interpretation – the extent that interpreting a previous semiotic mode required active cognition or a simple response.

To this was added a coding structure that reflected the process of scaffolding (Stålbrandt, 2007). This is important in the pedagogy of PBL as it is the means by which the facilitator guides student learning but allows them independence in terms of meaning making. In this case, five different approaches to scaffolding were identified:

Table 1: Different coding approaches for scaffolding

Category	Example from the transcripts
Conceptual Scaffolding (CS)	“that I’ve seen in my experience have been what I call box-shapes”
Metacognitive Scaffolding (MS)	“in order to get the result in force you need to know the angle too”
Procedural Scaffolding (PS)	“8.6 squared plus 7.4 [background noise] and the square root of all these”
Strategic Scaffolding (SS)	“so you could actually stand on a wire frame structure”
Technical Scaffolding (TS)	“you need to know your sine and cosine rules because in terms of the parallelograms that set up the forces”

The final coding element was a relatively simple description of who was interacting with whom. The options were facilitator to student; student to student or student to facilitator. This allowed a quick overview of the flow of the discussion and also allowed consideration of whether particular semiotic resources were deployed for particular interactions. Student-student interaction was also refined to allow a distinction between one to one discussions, an interaction with part of the whole group (i.e. between three or four of the students) and a whole group interaction.

Once the entire five sessions were coded, and seven excerpts (of 3-5 minutes in length) were selected for more detailed analysis. This selection was done as the intention was not just to rely on counting of instances in analysing the data but also to study the flow of interaction and how the semiotic mode in use reflected either the active participant or the task in hand. Equally, the excerpts were broken up into shorter segments and these segments were coded in terms of focus, who led the meaning making, type of interaction and who was present.

The selection process was non-random, and was designed to provide examples of all the different forms of interaction that were observed running from the facilitator making a presentation to the entire class to a sub-group of the students working on their own, as:

Table 2: Selection of excerpts for closer analysis

Excerpt # (Section No.)	Session #	Time*	Focus
1	1	01.25-04.00	Facilitator-led, focus on theory behind bridge design task
2	1	24.27-27.38	Interaction within student group, focus on theory behind bridge design task
3	1	54.21-56.27	Group-facilitator discussion, shift of focus from theory to model building task
4	2	30.50-36.15	Interaction within student group, followed by a group-facilitator discussion; shift of focus from theory to model building task
5	3	08.26-13.10	Shifts from student group, to facilitator’s input to group-facilitator discussion. Most of the focus is on the theory behind the bridge design
6	4	19.47-23.26	Two of the students discussing how to build the model
7	5	22.20-26.40	Group-Facilitator discussion focussed on the model designed between sessions 4 and 5

*Beginning and End times as per camcorder’s timer, with range corresponding to minutes and seconds into the session; the times coincide with the duration of the session, beginning with 0.00. Session refers to which of the five observed classes is being referred to.

Since the first session was important in terms of setting up the rules and constraints for the task, three separate excerpts were extracted. After that, each session is represented by a single excerpt. In turn, these larger excerpts were broken down for analysis into much shorter blocks (usually around a minute) as the overall process of meaning making altered. Each of these smaller blocks was then coded to show who had led the meaning making and the specific focus in each:

Table 3: Detailed Session coding and allocation

Block	Excerpt	Class	Time	Focus	Theory or Model Building	Dominated by
-	1	1	01.25-04.00	Facilitator Presentation (Whole class)	Theory	Facilitator
1	2	1	24.27-27.38	Student Interaction	Theory	Students
2	2	1	24.27-27.38	Student Interaction	Theory	Students
3	2	1	24.27-27.38	Student Interaction	Theory	Students
1	3	1	54.21-56.37	Facilitator Presentation (PBL group)	Model Building	Facilitator
2	3	1	54.21-56.37	Facilitator Presentation (PBL group)	Model Building	Facilitator
3	3	1	54.21-56.37	Facilitator Presentation (PBL group)	Model Building	Facilitator
4	3	1	54.21-56.37	Facilitator Presentation (PBL group)	Model Building	Facilitator (some student involvement)
1	4	2	30.50-36.15	Student Interaction	Theory	Students
2	4	2	30.50-36.15	Student Interaction	Theory	Students
3	4	2	30.50-36.15	Facilitator Presentation (PBL group)	Model Building	Facilitator (some student involvement)
1	5	3	08.26-12.51	Facilitator Presentation (PBL group)	Theory	Facilitator
2	5	3	08.26-12.51	Facilitator Presentation (PBL group)	Theory	Facilitator
3	5	3	08.26-12.51	Facilitator Presentation (PBL group)	Theory	Students (some facilitator involvement)
4	5	3	08.26-12.51	Facilitator Presentation (PBL group)	Theory	Students
1	6	4	19.47-23.26	Student Interaction	Model Building	Students
2	6	4	19.47-23.26	Student Interaction	Model Building	Students
3	6	4	19.47-23.26	Student Interaction	Model Building	Students
1	7	5	22.20-26.44	Facilitator Presentation (PBL group)	Model Building	Facilitator (some student involvement)
2	7	5	22.20-26.44	Facilitator Presentation (PBL group)	Model Building	Facilitator (some student involvement)
3	7	5	22.20-26.44	Facilitator Presentation (PBL group)	Model Building	Facilitator (some student involvement)

*As per camcorder's timer; the times coincide with the duration of the session, beginning with 0.00.

This shows the development of the excerpts and the main categorisations in terms of e focus and who can be seen to have dominated each segment (domination is derived from a combination of the number of semiotic modes used and a qualitative judgement as to the relative importance of the flow of interaction).

Hypotheses

One goal of this study was to understand how semiotic modes in use vary either according to role, changes in task or to reflect the wider environment. In this case, the meaning making and problem solving took place in the context of a PBL class as part of the first year of a university engineering course. As a result, while it was expected that environment would influence the meaning making approach it was not expected that this would shift in the limited timespan and focus of this study (i.e. the same students were not also studied in a different module or outside university). This left three sources of variation:

1. On the basis of role, there the two formal roles are student and facilitator;
2. On the basis of individual character (ie did the five students all use similar meaning making strategies);
3. On the basis of task, in effect the transition observed between the theory of forces and bridge design and the practical task of building the model bridge.

From this, three basic hypotheses were developed to understand the interaction between context, task and individuals:

1. If there was no difference in the semiotic resources used by the facilitator or the students, we can conclude that role plays no part in the meaning making process;
2. If all five students use the same semiotic resources we can conclude that individual differences play no role;
3. If the same semiotic modes are used in both the theory discussions and the practical discussions we can conclude that task plays no role in the selection of semiotic resources.

Findings

Differences Between the Facilitator and the Students

As expected this offered clear evidence of very different uses of semiotic resources including:

- He is usually is seeking to collaborate with the students (i.e. he is not making meaning just for himself but to guide their learning);
- He rarely simply agrees with a statement by one of the students (this can be either a statement of relative power or that, in most instances, he is seeking to elaborate on their question and help them develop their understanding). The latter interpretation is supported by his frequent use of complex interpretation in his speech; and
- He makes substantial use of scaffolding, drawing on both verbal and non-verbal resources, as he seeks to guide and indirectly lead the students' meaning making.

Differences Between the Students

There are a number of ways to analyse if student meaning making shifted according to their own approach to the task. The simplest is to count the number of instances of verbal and non-verbal meaning making in four of the classes observed (the fourth class is excluded as only two of the students were present at that stage).

Figure 2: Volumes of Verbal and Non-Verbal meaning making

This presents strong evidence that not all the students undertook the task in the same manner. Student E was often working on his own, using a laptop when the others were working with pen and paper and he was rarely being involved even when more than two of the other students were discussing their progress or interacting with the facilitator. This relative silence by some of the students has been regularly observed as an

issue in PBL classes (Remedios, Clarke, & Hawthorne, 2008). However, since one of the ‘silent’ students used his laptop to search for possible bridge designs, he nevertheless participated in the learning process, even though with a very low level of engagement. This supports what other studies found. For example, Jun’s study (Jun, 2012) found that silence is a communicative approach, and a method of engagement. Remedios, Clarke & Hawthorne (2008) argue that silence should not be considered as a lack of learning. As a result, it can be concluded that as long as students work non-verbally, they are engaging in the PBL process.

Overall, this provides evidence that the active (and shared) student meaning was mainly carried out by three of the group of five, with one (Student E) making a single statement and another (Student C) making seven statements. The extent that some students are ‘silent’ becomes even more obvious if only those excerpts coded as ‘student dominated’ (i.e. where the facilitator takes no part) are taken into account (again this excludes Session 4 as that only includes two of the students).

Figure 3: Student Meaning Making when facilitator is absent

This shows that only two of the students are active in the verbal meaning making when the student group is working on its own. Two of the others (Student C and Student D) are mostly silent and one, Student E, makes no comments at all. This also indicates very different levels of activity for students B and D depending on whether or not the facilitator is present. Student B makes two utterances when the facilitator is present and 25 when he is absent. By contrast, Student D makes 30 utterances when the facilitator is present and only one when he is absent.

Differences Between Task Formulation

The final way to study the impact of context on semiotic use is to consider if these shift as the task develops. A key aspect to this class was the relative development of the task from a set of theoretical precepts (about stresses and forces) to actually building a model bridge that would be tested. Taking this perspective, there are substantial differences in the meaning making approach adopted both by the facilitator and the students. The facilitator makes use of different scaffolding strategies (table 1) as the task develops. For example, when the focus is on the theory, he relies on technical scaffolding, such as: “so you work out the force against the other members (08.33, session 3, block 2)” and “what you need to do is to work out a balance (09.40, session 3, block 2)” and both statements are both reinforced either by pointing in a particular direction or referring to a OHP slide. In effect, in the theory sections, he tends to use scaffolding approaches that are basically based on speech, complemented with non-verbal gestures. However, in the discussions about building the model there is a shift to much more substantial use of non-verbal resources. In effect, not only is there a link between the scaffolding strategy in use and the method but that this reflects the focus as:

Figure 4: Facilitator use of mode and scaffolding approach

The students too show a shift in meaning making approach between the theory and the practical sections. The later is much more likely to be dominated by non-verbal or to be intermodal (ie balanced) whereas the theory discussions are more dominated by verbal meaning making.

Figure 5: Shifting modes of student meaning making

Discussion

Context

In general, this research emphasises the importance of both resemiosis and intersemiosis in understanding the usage of semiotic modes in meaning making. First, the context matters. Here, meaning making takes place in a number of circumscribed ways. It is a university class in engineering where the linkage between theory and practical application is a major feature. Even though PBL stresses the importance of student led problem solving, the reality is this takes place in a context. Here that is provided by the task rules and the need to keep to an academic timetable. At the end of the first class, the facilitator sets out the task rules:

Listen guys, there's a number 275 paddle-pop sticks, now glue doesn't weigh much, so in the test procedure. The bridge is weighed. So if it's too bloody heavy it won't even get tested, you get fail. So be careful of the paddle-pop sticks, make sure that you don't go over the 275. ... Here it's going to be weighed and loaded, there's a penalty for weight. (Facilitator's input, Session 1, Timer 44.03)

Individual Differences

Despite having notionally the same task environment, there is also strong evidence that student meaning making alters, as does their learning styles. Overall, there appear to be four different learning approaches evident within the group of five students. These preferred approaches are evident in the level of the students' engagement across different modalities and in different forms of group formation and interaction. One approach is evidenced by Student A. He is best characterised as a *fully multimodally engaged learner*. He engaged in the PBL task actively both verbally and non-verbally.

The second approach is evidenced by Student B, who can be described as an *engaged peer learner*. This is because he engaged far more when the PBL team worked independently from the facilitator than when the facilitator was present with the team. Students C and E are the least engaged students verbally and non-verbally. However, Student C is more active than Student E. This is particularly obvious through the use of non-verbal semiotic resources. Both Students C and E can best be characterised though as *passive* or *'silent' learners* (Remedios, et al., 2008). Student D provides a contrast to Student B, in particular and is best understood as a *facilitator-focused learner*. This nomenclature is proposed because he engaged verbally with the PBL team primarily when the facilitator was present and virtually not at all when the facilitator was absent. It appears as if it was important for him for the facilitator to observe his participation. However, it is important to note that he was a considerable contributor to the meaning making non-verbally, being the second highest among the students in his non-verbal turns.

Overall, this provides strong evidence that even when the task rules are closely defined, multimodal analysis allows a careful exploration not just as to if there remain individual differences but how these differences are manifested.

Conclusions

Overall, the three hypotheses are supported by the evidence. The context affects the meaning making and sets the rules by which both students and facilitator act. Despite this, there is strong evidence of individual differences in meaning making in terms of: volume; spread between verbal and non-verbal; interaction with the student group or interaction with the facilitator. Finally, the semiotic modes adopted shift as the task develops from consideration of the theory to the practical task of constructing the model bridge.

Most of the time both verbal and non-verbal semiotic resources are adopted and overall the dominant mode (Iedema, 2003) varies. In the theoretical sessions, speech tends to dominate, but in some instances non-verbal gestures and tools are essential to support the meaning making. In the practical sessions either there is a balance in the importance of the two modes or in some instances the non-verbal mode is dominant and speech used simply to vocalise the meaning that is being constructed using gesture and the tools. This indicates there are three different forms of interaction between verbal and non-verbal meaning making emerged, that is 3 distinct modes of multimodal meaning making:

- 1) *Verbal-dominant*, but re-semiotised non-verbally - instances where the verbal element carried the main meaning-making role and the non-verbal aspect was secondary;
- 2) *Non-verbal-dominant*, but re-semiotised verbally - instances where the non-verbal element carried the main meaning-making role and the verbal aspect was secondary; and
- 3) *Intermodal* – meaning making is truly multimodal - instances where both verbal and non-verbal modes were essential and mutually interdependent in the construction and interpretation of meaning.

Need for More Research

Some of the findings in this study are common in the PBL literature. In particular, the tension for the facilitator between allowing student led problem solving and the demands of the academic setting and the problem that some students do not engage with the shared group aspect of the task. Although this study offers strong evidence for the importance of the task, individual differences and varying focus on the selection of semiotic resources, there is a need to conduct similar research in other settings. In particular, this would help to explore the relative importance of these three constraints, something that a single study cannot explore.

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